

PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF UZBEK LINGUISTICS

Sarsenbayev Khamudulla Abdullayevich

Tashkent Chemical Technology Institute

Assistant teacher of Department of Foreign languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11500616>

Annotation: This article covers topics such as the origin and development of the language, as well as the great services of scientists and scholars who contributed to the development of the language.

Key words: Linguistics, Ferdinand De Saussure, Turkic languages, integration, problems of linguistics.

Introduction:

Language is the most important tool in human relations. It was formed during the stages of development of the society and served the interests of all mankind. The emergence and development of a language is directly related to the development of society. Also, the source of learning of all sciences that think about human development is related to language. Different definitions of language have been given in different periods, but until now there is no clear and unified definition. For this reason, this issue is the cause of intense debate among many scientists and scientific researchers. In addition, issues such as the subject, object, and tasks of linguistics depend to some extent on how to understand language. As mentioned above, due to different definitions, the subject of linguistics was also perceived differently. From that time, linguistic science was thoroughly researched.

Since the 20th century, a new era has begun in defining the subject of linguistics. In particular, the theory of the Swiss scientist Ferdinand de Saussure, who is the founder of modern linguistics, made a unique turn in the subject matter of linguistics. This scientist's contribution to science is significant in that he was the first to determine that language is a complex phenomenon and created a new perfect, clearly formed theory of general linguistics. Ferdinand de Saussure expresses the following thoughts about language: "*according to its function in human society, language is a tool of communication, a means of expressing ideas, in terms of its social nature, language is a pure sign system according to the internal structure of cultural-historical and social phenomena.*" At the same time, it should be said that Uzbek scientists and thinkers also occupy a special place in the formation of the language.

In particular, our classical writer Alisher Navoi, who created in the second half of the 15th century, wrote works in the Turkish language and played an

important role in the development of this language. Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur described it as follows: "*Alisherbek was a person without equal. He even recited poems in the Turkish language, and no one spoke much and well*". After Navoi, a number of our thinkers contributed to the development of the Uzbek language, but still Alisher Navoi remained the owner of an inimitable pen in the Turkish language. The reason is that at that time, great figures, poets, writers and even kings had a wrong attitude towards the Turkish language and did not believe that they could create a meaningful and meaningful work in this language. And Alisher Navoi wrote an invaluable work like "Khamisa" in Turkish language, leaving behind "*Khamisa*" written before him. In this way, he proved to those who belittle the Turkish language as a "rough language" that this language has value, importance and unlimited possibilities.

In addition, Navoi's lyric poems are collected in eight divans, seven of which are Turkish lyrics. After such an event, many creators are convinced that the Turkish language is rich in words, artistic and beautiful expressions, and among a number of scholars, writers such as Munis, Ogakhi, Khorezmi, Hamid Balkhi, Amiri, Mashrab are unique in the Turkish language. created examples of creativity. On the other hand, their works serve as the main factor in the emergence of specific norms and procedures in the perfect formation of the Uzbek language. At the same time, Alisher Navoi, as a linguist scientist, wrote the work "*Mukhokamat ul-lughatayn*". This book reflects the formation of the Uzbek literary language, his experiences in the field of language, and his deep scientific and theoretical views.

Nowadays, if we want to conduct any research, scientific research in linguistics or Uzbek classical literature, we will definitely turn to the work of Alisher Navoi and other thinkers. Their masterpieces dedicated to linguistics have a high place not only in our country, but also in European countries. It should be noted that the interest in the Uzbek language in foreign countries is increasing day by day. This process, of course, does not occur by itself. There are such lovers of the Uzbek language on the borders of our country that, while living in foreign countries, they do not forget the respect for our mother tongue and promote this language in foreign countries as well. In 1960, he graduated from the Tashkent State Institute of Foreign Languages (*now the University of World Languages*) and began working at the Faculty of Turkology of the Tashkent State University. He was forced to leave his country in 1990 due to unjust accusations during the war. This scientist, who settled in the USA, starts teaching the Uzbek language to students at Indiana University in America. In the

fall of 2002, as a result of his tireless work, this scientist was hired as a teacher at the Department of Asian Languages and Cultures at the University of Wisconsin in the USA.

During the 18 years spent abroad, the professor created more than ten books and hundreds of articles on the Uzbek language and literature, published in Uzbek and English. In addition, it will familiarize the Uzbek people with the resources considered important for Central Asia and the specific values of the West. One of the major achievements of the linguist scientist Khairulla Ismatulla was the publication of the two-volume "Uzbek language" textbook. Currently, this book is widely used in many American institutions. The scientific research conducted by this hard-working scientist for the development of our country has borne fruit. In particular, Federic Starr, Edward Allworth, Mark Brill Olcott, N. Karpat, Mark Katz, John Schoberlagen, Bill Fairman, Martin Spicher, Zino Baran and other famous scientists conducted research on the Uzbek language and wrote many articles and works. For example, the book "Current Uzbeks" by Edward Allworth is one of them. In addition, Mavlon Shukurzoda's book "Grammar of the Uzbek language" is of great interest to American educators. Also G'. Abdurahmonov, A. Rustamov's work "Ancient Turkic language" and a number of scientific works of Haydarali Uzgkov are kept as priceless treasures at Indiana University, which shows how powerful and popular the field of science is in this country called Uzbekistan. Although the popularity of our Uzbek language is an epic for the whole world, there are also problems related to our language.

Although the creation of modern technology tools serves to facilitate all aspects of our life, today this very technology is the cause of urgent problems in the Uzbek language. At first, people used to communicate with each other through letters. At the same time, SMS service on mobile phones has become everyone's "happy assistant". Thanks to such technological tools, we are increasingly forgetting the normative rules of our language. When sending messages using a mobile communication tool, we rarely observe spelling errors and punctuation marks. Many words and letters are misspelled. For example, in the messages of the mobile communication tool, the letter "w" is used instead of the letter "sh", the number 6 is used instead of the letter "o", the word "with" is in the form of "bn", and the word "need" is " Its use in the form of "k\k" is becoming very popular among young people. If we do not put an end to this situation, we may forget to write correctly in Uzbek. However, all mobile devices

have all punctuation marks. This situation has become the center of controversy many times. But it still has not found its solution as a problem.

From the point of view of today's developing times, we can say that the younger generation, in general, all people use technology tools like computers, mobile phones, fax and pocket computers more than paper documents. Of course, we cannot deny being in step with the times. But we cannot ignore the rules of the Uzbek language, which the whole world is looking at with admiration. Our Uzbek language is our pride, a symbol of our nation's existence. In conclusion, we should focus on solving the above-mentioned problems.

References:

1. Azizov O. "Introduction to Linguistics" T., 1996
2. Abduazizov A.A. Introduction to Linguistics. - T., 1999
3. Akshina A.A. Manual for the course "Introduction to Linguistics" - M., 1969.
4. Baskakov N.A., Sodikov A.S. "General Linguistics".-T., 1979.
5. Kholmanova Z. T. Introduction to Linguistics. Tashkent - 2007.
6. N. Turniyozov. Introduction to Linguistics. The text of the lectures. Samarkand - 2005.

WOC
**WORLD
ONLINE
CONFERENCES**

